

Misuse of the term 'molecularity' as applied to elementary reactions : An opinion

Y. K. Gupta*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

Manuscript received 16 May 2007, accepted 20 June 2007

Keywords : Molecularity, order of a reaction, stoichiometry, chemical education.

The IUPAC definition¹, of 'molecularity' of elementary reactions is 'the number of reactant particles that are involved in the microscopic event'. It is also 'the number of reactant particles present in the transition state'. Reactant particles may be molecules as well as atoms. The difficulty in appreciating the nomenclature 'molecularity' lies in the meaning of the word 'molecule' from which 'molecularity' has been derived. A sample survey of about hundred chemistry teachers from Northern India has revealed that chemists in general do not know the definition. Kineticists know it but they have their reservation for regarding a reacting particle, which may be an atom, as a molecule because atoms, though being particles, are not molecules.

When 'molecule' was defined as 'particle' no 'atom' seems to have been known or defined, and therefore, the term, 'molecule' could be freely used to mean 'smallest particle' but subsequently 'atom' as understood then was also included in the meaning of 'molecule' since it was a particle. However, once we know the chemical definition of 'molecule' as 'group of atoms' and 'atom' as atom rather than particle, confusion starts in using the non-chemical definition in the elementary reactions. In other words we are made to use a different definition of 'molecule' though we already know the chemical definition. In fact no chemist even in spite of knowing 'molecule' as a particle, is prepared to define it so since he/she is well aware of the chemical meaning.

Another confusion was created when van't Hoff² used the term 'molecularity' and Ostwald³ used the term, 'order of reaction' to correlate the rate-dependence of the reaction on the concentration of a reactant. The two were numerically the same for the few reactions known then. The problem is that van't Hoff probably used the par-

ticle-definition of molecule and Ostwald employed the chemical-definition. So once again the same small group of chemists (kineticists) arbitrarily used one of the two definitions of the molecule, showing the confusion that existed then. However, the mistake was soon recognized by the chemists and the rate-dependence on the concentration of a reactant as 'molecularily' was dropped.

It is not only the kineticists but chemists too, in general, that fail to appreciate the meaning of molecularity. They seem to describe 'molecularity' as one derived from 'molecule' a term of very common usage. Few chemists only associate 'molecularity' with elementary reactions. On the other hand there are only a few elementary reactions. The use of the term 'molecularity' therefore, has a very limited use and it is only a kineticist familiar with elementary reactions, who can define and appreciate the term. For such a situation, for such a constrained definition of the term and for such restricted applicability, there does not seem any justification in retaining the term with the present meaning. Since 'molecularity' is associated with molecule – a term of very wide coverage, chemists rightly or wrongly confuse it with stoichiometry. The confusion may not be justified, yet it does exist there on account of the application of the definition to a very limited area and because only a few chemists are required to know it and use it and because 'molecularity' is part of stoichiometry of an elementary reaction. One may argue why bother for modifying or giving up this definition of 'molecularity' if it is meant for a small group of chemists, the 'kineticists'. It is okay but why employ then this term only which is derived from a very familiar word 'molecule' used by chemists in general at every step of their work? Why not use another term which has one meaning and is confusion-free? If one gives the name

*Present address : J/5, Phase II, Shivalik Nagar, Hardwar-249 403, Uttarakhand, India.

'particularity' to the number of reacting particles in the elementary reaction, it would make no difference for kineticists and more significantly no difference to chemists in general.

We again have a problem in naming the theories of reaction-rates as theory of unimolecular reactions, theory of bimolecular reactions and so on. The reacting species are not necessarily molecules. These can be atoms too. Once again the definition of 'molecule' used here is 'particle' and not chemical. And the farce is that in practice the results of these theories are applied to a single rate determining step of a composite reaction which forms part of the mechanism but the step is not the elementary reaction studied experimentally. From all this it appears that molecule is no more than a particle. The paradox is that the chemists in general know it only as a group of 'atoms'. Also the concept of 'molecularity' serves no purpose in the study of kinetics and in the understanding of mechanism.

As a matter of fact the definition of 'molecularity' in a way is stoichiometry of elementary reaction. Since stoichiometry is a well defined term in chemistry, it would clarify matters if we give a different name to the stoichiometry of an elementary reaction. Unimolecular reactions may be known as uni-particle reactions, bimolecular reactions may be known as bi-particle reactions and so on. The theories may also be named accordingly. Such

an identification instead of using 'molecularity' is free of any ambiguity about the meaning of molecule and one can use it with one meaning anywhere in the domain of chemistry. Thus it may be a little unusual for the kineticists to use this new term 'particularity' but it saves a big section of chemists from the inconvenience in defining the term 'molecularity'.

It may not be out of place to mention that the terms 'order' and 'molecularity' are often mentioned together⁴, though neither there is similarity between them nor do they have opposite meanings or are inter-dependent. Order is empirical and 'molecularity' is a theoretical concept. They refer to two different types of reactions, complex and elementary respectively. On the other hand 'order' and 'stoichiometry' go very well together. They may refer to the same overall reaction irrespective of its simplicity or complexity.

References

1. International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry, Appendix V (provisional), Symbols and Terminology in Chemical Kinetics, Pergamon Press, 1989, p. 759.
2. K. J. Laidler, "Chemical Kinetics", Harper and Row International, New York, 3rd ed., 1987, p. 495.
3. Ref. 2, p. 497.
4. A. A. Frost and R. G. Pearson, "Kinetics and Mechanism", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1970, p. 10.